

CONNECTIVITY

RESOURCES

NEEDS

OBSTACLES

DIGITAL LONDON

OBSTACLES

NEEDS

RESOURCES

INFORMATION

EDUCATION

INTELLIGENCE

HEALTH

CULTURE

CONNECTIVITY

RESOURCES

FEASIBLE

UNSAFE / UNFEASIBLE

OBSTACLES / CHALLENGES

